

DESIGN OPTIMIZATION OF A BOGIE STRUCTURE FOR A TRADE-OFF BETWEEN PROCESSING TIME AND STRUCTUREAL PROPETY

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ABSTRACT

In the present railroad industry, weight reduction is the main issue in developing a vehicle structure. Train vehicle is composed of car body, wheel set and bogie system. Among them, bogie system has a great influence to a ride comfort by affecting vibration characteristics as well as reduction of power consumption through weight reduction. Korea Railroad Research Institute (KRRI) has developed a bogie system by autoclave molding process with composite material and obtained the satisfactory mechanical properties. Now, KRRI is in applying Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) process to improve productivity to manufacture a bogie system. Manufacturing process of bogie system by RTM process was analyzed numerically in the preliminary study. In RTM process, productivity or process time depends on the fiber volume fraction and inlet pressure as process condition. To control process time, thickness of a product can be considered as a design parameter to consider both of fiber volume fraction and inlet pressure. At this time, a final product weight can be varied according to thickness and mechanical properties of a final product also can be. Therefore, productivity, product weight and mechanical property are coupled together and simultaneous optimization should be considered to obtain a tradeoff between them. In this study, the optimal product design (thickness design) plan was suggested to consider processing time, weight and mechanical properties. RTM process for a bogie system was analyzed by ANSYS and a tendency of processing time depending on thickness was induced and mechanical properties were analyzed by ABAQUS. Based on the results of processing time and mechanical properties, optimization method can be proposed and applied to a simultaneous problem between process and structural properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the present railroad industry, weight reduction is an interesting subject to make a car body or engine system lighter. Rail condition is affected by weight of train vehicle and it is concerned to train operators due to the increasing maintenance cost. Therefore, railroad car builders are interested in making lighter cars and they start to care about composite material to replace the typical metal material. So far, composite material is confined to the car body or the parts in car body mainly. However, it starts to make the drive system such as a bogie system with composite material. In this case, due to the characteristics of composite material, some suspension parts can be removed and total

bogie system can be simplified. Korea Railroad Research Institute (KRRRI) made bogie system without first suspension system by applying composite material. In present, running test is being performed. In this case, autoclave moulding process was adopted to make bogie structure. Bogie structure made by KRRRI is shown in Fig.1.

Figure 1: Bogie structure manufactured by autoclave moulding process

In autoclave moulding process, uni-directional fiberglass prepregs are stacked around core made with foam and already cured composite panels for side beam. For cross beam, inner skin is made by staking prepregs. Thereafter, side and cross beams are attached each other by adhesive process and outer skin with prepregs is wrapped around the inner product. RTM process in which we are interested in this study replaces autoclave moulding process to make outer skin. By RTM process, the processing time can be reduced. In this study, we analyse the process characteristic (i.e. processing time) based on the thickness of structure to minimize it when RTM process is applied to a bogie outer skin. Structure properties can be also changed according to the thickness, and this is another target to maximize by adjusting design variable of thickness. The final target of this study is to suggest the optimization methodology to trade off both of them.

2 PROCESS ANALYSIS

Darcy's law is the governing equation of fluid flow to express fluid flow to penetrate into the porous media. Flow velocity is in inverse proportion to fluid viscosity and in proportion to pressure gradient and permeability.

$$\bar{v} = -\frac{K}{\mu} \nabla P$$

\bar{v} : superficial velocity
 μ : fluid viscosity
 ∇P : pressure gradient
 K : permeability

(1)

And the permeability can be determined in Kozeny-Carman equation.

$$K = \frac{d_f^2 (1 - v_f)^3}{16k v_f^2}$$

d_f : fiber diameter
 v_f : fiber volume fraction
 k : Kozeny constant

(2)

Kozeny constant is not same in every direction of fibre mat. Gebart[1] proposed equations in each direction of fiber mat.

Skin of a bogie frame for RTM to make is shown in Fig. 2.

Core of bogie frame is manufactured by stacking prepregs and foams for side beam and stacking prepregs only for cross beam. Then they are adhered by adhesive and wrapped into one structure by RTM.

Figure 2: Skin of bogie frame

Horizontal and vertical thicknesses of side and cross beams are defined as design variables and filling time is analysed in various cases.

Stacking orientation of fibre mat is considered as the same number of 0° and 90° degree fibre mat. And the final permeability is calculated as the mean value of both orientation permeability. The thickness to be considered is 15mm, 17.5mm and 20mm

Fibre volume fraction is 60% for 15mm thickness, 51% for 17.5mm and 45% for 20mm. Fibre volume fraction gradually decreases as thickness increases due to the constant fibre mat number.

Conditions for analysis are shown in Table 1 and permeability according to the thickness is shown in Table 2.

Resin density	Resin viscosity	Porosity (vf 60%)	Inlet pressure	Outlet pressure	Inlet diameter
1.08	0.15Pa.s	0.4	4bar	-1bar	20mm

Table 1: Processing conditions of numerical analysis

Thickness(mm)	Volume fraction	k11	k22	Mean k
15	60	1.72E-11	1.77E-13	8.69E-12
17.5	51	2.58E-11	6.06E-13	1.32E-11
20	45	3.54E-11	1.31E-12	1.84E-11

Table 2: Permeability for each thickness

Process analysis was performed by ANSYS Fluent and only a quarter of bogie frame according to the symmetric planes. Location of gate is shown in Fig. 3 and vent is located in middle location between gates at the bottom of frame.

Figure 3: Analysis domain of a bogie frame

Filling time result for each case is summarized in Table 2.

	Horizontal surface thickness (mm)	Vertical surface thickness (mm)	Filling time (sec)
Case 1	15	15	35111
Case 2	15	17.5	29608
Case 3	15	20	27885
Case 4	17.5	15	16786
Case 5	17.5	17.5	10129
Case 6	17.5	20	8758
Case 7	20	17.5	6035
Case 8	20	20	4676

Table 2: Case definition and filling time result

Figure 4: Processing time for each case

As we can see in Fig. 4, increasing thickness shows the shorter filling time. It is because volume fraction decreases when the number of fiber mat is constant as thickness increases. And it increases permeability which results into the decrease of flow resistance.

3 STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

Structural property is another characteristic which is influenced by the thickness. In the previous chapter, processing time was considered as the target to minimize. However, it can be admitted only when it satisfies the structural requirement. As well as the process analysis, structural analysis should be considered for optimization of both properties.

Figure 5: Section of bogie frame and load condition for static analysis

For structural analysis, the core and outer skin of bogie frame is considered together. The section of bogie frame is shown in Fig. 5. Skin thickness for structural analysis is 15mm.

Material properties of skin and foam core are shown in Table 3.

Material properties	GEP224(glass/epoxy)	Foam core
E_{11} (GPa)	34.4	0.084
E_{22} (GPa)	13.2	0.084
G_{12} (GPa)	7.05	0.038
G_{13} (GPa)	7.05	0.038
G_{23} (GPa)	7.05	0.038
ν_{12}	0.27	0.11

Table 3: Material properties of skin and foam core

Composite core is considered as quasi-isotropic material with $E=23.8$ GPa and $\nu=0.27$.

For static analysis, ABAQUS/standard is used in which 3D solid element is used for composite and foam core and shell element for composite skin. Stacking sequence is expressed in Fig.5.

Displacement in the middle of side beam of frame is 7.17mm and Tsai-Wu failure criterion is less than 0.14. The simulation result is shown in Fig.6.

Figure 6: Displacement and Tsai-Wu failure criterion

4 OPTIMIZATION

The trade-off between process and structure is carried out by simultaneous optimization. The target is to search for the optimum thickness to satisfy processing time and structural property at the same time. It can be solved as a multi-objective optimization problem. Alternatively, it can be defined as a single objective optimization with some constraints.

For optimization, processing and structural analysis should be performed at every iteration step of each design variable. It requires a long computation time and it is not desirable. Therefore, from the case study of processing and structural analysis, relation between design variables and processing time and structural property is analogized. Optimization scheme is shown in Fig.7.

Figure 7: Simultaneous optimization scheme between process and structure

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, RTM process is considered as a proper process to manufacture a train bogie frame. To control process time, thickness of a product is defined as design variables. And through case study, quantitative relation between thickness and processing time is induced. Structural property can be also expressed in terms of thickness of structure and estimated for simultaneous optimization. Based on the results of processing time and mechanical properties depending on the thickness, optimization method can be proposed and applied to a simultaneous problem between process and structural properties. At present, the optimization problem is being studied.

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